

Expanding the Horizon : Evidences in Maxillary Expansion Treatment

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Abstract

Maxillary Transverse Deficiency (MTD) is a common orthodontic condition characterized by a reduced transverse dimension of the maxillary arch, affecting both dental and skeletal structures. Its prevalence ranges from 13–23% in children and up to 30% in adults. The condition arises from multi-factorial causes, including genetic, developmental, traumatic, and iatrogenic factors, and may be associated with nasal septum deviation. This review explores the etiology, diagnosis, treatment modalities, and bio-mechanical implications of various expansion techniques including Slow Maxillary Expansion (SME), Rapid Maxillary Expansion (RME), Mini-screw Assisted Rapid Palatal Expansion (MARPE), and Surgically Assisted Rapid Palatal Expansion (SARPE). Based on the evidences, treatment modality must be customized considering skeletal maturation and specific dental needs.

Keywords: Maxillary Expansion; Rapid Maxillary Expansion; Slow Maxillary Expansion; MARPE; SARPE.

Introduction

Transverse discrepancies in the maxillary arch are among the most frequently encountered challenges in orthodontics. These abnormalities, often manifesting as posterior crossbites or arch constriction can affect both the dental occlusion and skeletal harmony of the craniofacial complex. While various techniques exist to correct MTD, selection of the appropriate treatment modality depends upon the age, growth stage, and type of malocclusion.

For more than a century, transverse deficiencies of the maxilla have been treated using various forms of expansion therapy. The concept was first introduced by Angell in 1860 and later brought into mainstream orthodontics by Haas in 1961¹.

Although initially met with criticism, maxillary expansion has become a well established, straightforward and reliable treatment method. To correct transverse discrepancies, the palate is often widened using a combination of orthodontic and orthopedic forces.

Interestingly, different studies have elicited varied effects of maxillary expansion on sagittal and vertical dimensions based on lateral cephalometric measurements. Haas (1961) and Davis and Kroman (1969) stated that the maxilla moved downward and forward. Silva Filho et al (1991) found that the maxilla rotated downwards and backwards but did not change sagittally.

Wertz (1970) and Dreskin (1977) concluded that the maxilla moved downward and backward in some patients and downward and forward in others following RPE. Wertz (1970) established that the maxillary incisors retrocline following RPE Sandikcioglu and Hazar in (1997) inferred maxillary incisors proclined following RPE.

Sarver and Johnston (1989) found maxilla moved backward in some bonded RPE cases. Sevil Akkaya et al (1999) stated that the maxilla moved forward and the mandible moved backward following RPE with an increase in ANB angle and mandibular plane angle.

Isao Shundo et al (2012) witnessed spontaneous expansion of the mandibular arch concurrent with maxillary expansion in the early mixed dentition patients with maxillary incisor crowding was seen following slow maxillary expansion with quad helix.

Saori Endo et al (2016) found significant decrease in the mandibular plane angle in hyperdivergent patients following quad helix appliance. Jared K. Corbridge et al (2016) affirmed substantial decreases in buccal bone thickness and increases in lingual bone thick-

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ness following slow maxillary expansion treatment.

Clinical Relevance of Maxillary Expansion

Maxillary expansion plays a critical role in the correction of transverse maxillary deficiencies, which are commonly associated with posterior crossbites, V-shaped narrow palatal vault, crowding, and airway obstruction. Expansion therapy not only improves occlusal function and dental alignment but also has significant effects on nasal airflow and airway volume, contributing to better respiratory function in select patients.

Liptook identified basic clinical features, including difficulty with nasal breathing, the volume of the nasal cavity reduced, breathing from the mouth, a narrow hard palate, and cone-shaped hypertrophy. The existence of at least two clinical features mentioned previously designates skeletal or dentoskeletal malocclusion and demands treatment which focuses on enlarging the transverse maxillary measurements.

Patient's age is of utmost importance when selecting treatment appliances. By the age of six years, normal palatal development is almost complete. Post puberty, the mid-palatal suture gradually becomes interdigitated, eventually making separation difficult. The posterior teeth are not able to move during the application of heavy or rapidly accelerating forces. Therefore, the forces are concentrated in the mid-palatine suture. The suture splits open when the forces exceed the limit required for sutural resistance and tooth movement, whilst the teeth barely move.

In addition to constriction of the periodontal ligament fibers, the alveolar process is bent by appliance, anchor teeth tipping, and the mid-palatine suture is opened gradually and other maxillary sutures². Maxillary expansion impacts various surrounding structures, including the mid-palatine suture, palate, maxilla, mandible, temporomandibular joint, and both upper anterior and posterior teeth. Additionally, it can affect speech and hearing.

In 1886, According to Plaff, Lohman, and Derichsweiler, the first rhinologist, Eysell of Berlin suggested the possibility of separation of the maxillae influencing the inner conformation of the nose. He was met with utter skepticism on the part of his confreres and eventually gave up on the idea³.

In 1903, G.V.I. Brown stated that with the aid of pressure which is gently applied resulting in no pain but little inconvenience, it is possible in all young persons to force the maxillaries apart by separating the median suture extending between the incisor teeth and through the part of the hard palate. This was in accordance to the evidence that central incisors were moved apart without any attachment to them or by direct pressure being applied to them.

Intranasal measurements were made by Wright, on over thirty patients treated for nasal insufficiency by rapid expansion procedures. The distance between antral walls below the inferior nasal concha and found increments up to 6.5 mm. Evidence showed increased width and from slight to marked improvement in intranasal respiration⁴.

Following Brown's method, Willis reported a case of a female unable to do physical work because of difficulty in breathing. Using Brown's technique he separated the maxillae in three weeks to a distance that allowed the passing of a lead pencil barrel between the central incisors. This was appreciated through the illustrations of plaster models.

Types of Maxillary Expansion

Currently, four main techniques are commonly used for maxillary expansion:

1. Slow Maxillary Expansion (SME)
2. Rapid Maxillary Expansion (RME)

3. Mini-screw Assisted Rapid Palatal Expansion (MARPE)
4. Surgically Assisted Rapid Maxillary Expansion (SARPE)

Indications for Maxillary Expansion

Maxillary expansion is indicated in the following cases:

1. **Transverse Maxillary Deficiency**
Often presenting with unilateral or bilateral posterior crossbite.
2. **Dental Crowding**
Expansion can create additional space to alleviate moderate anterior crowding without extractions.
3. **Nasal Airway Obstruction / Mouth Breathing**
Expansion may improve nasal airflow by increasing nasal cavity volume.
4. **Class III Malocclusion (Compensatory Cases)**
When the transverse discrepancy contributes to the Class III appearance.
5. **Obstructive Sleep Apnea (In Pediatric Cases)**
As part of airway-focused orthodontic management.

Anatomy and Growth of the Maxilla

The maxillary complex is attached to the cranial base thereby there is a strong influence of the latter on the former. Although there is no sharp line of demarcation between the cranium & maxillary growth gradients, yet the position of the maxilla is dependent upon the growth at spheno-occipital & spheno-ethmoid synchondroses.

The growth of nasomaxillary complex comprises of two aspects with regard to the displacement in the position of the maxillary complex. Firstly, Primary displacement occurs in a forward direction. This occurs due to the growth of the maxillary tuberosity in a posterior direction. This results in the whole maxilla being carried anteriorly. And the Secondary displacement, which occurs in a downward & forward direction as the cranial base grows⁵.

Maxilla is related to cranium at least partially by the, fronto-nasal suture, fronto-maxillary suture, zygomaticotemporal suture zygomaticomaxillary suture, pterygopalatine suture. These sutures are all oblique & more or less parallel with each other. The growth in these areas would serve to move the maxilla downward & forward.

The tenacity of circum maxillary attachments due to buttressing is strong postero-superomedially and postero-superolaterally.

A palatine bone forms an intimate relationship with maxilla to form complete hard palate (or) floor of nose and greater part of lateral wall of nasal cavity.

It articulates anteriorly with maxilla through transverse palatal sutures and posteriorly through pterygoid process of the sphenoid bone.

The interpalatine suture joins the two palatine bones at their horizontal plates and continuous as inter maxillary sutures.

These sutures forms the junction of three opposing pairs of bones: the pre-maxillae, maxilla, and the palatine. The entire forms mid-palatal suture⁶.

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The maxilla is connected to the cranium and cranial base by a number of sutures:

- Nasomaxillary Suture
- Frontomaxillary Suture
- Zygomaticotemporal Suture
- Lacrimomaxillary Suture
- Ethmoidomaxillary Suture

- Vomeromaxillary Suture

Mid Palatine Suture plays a key role in R.M.E. Shape of suture varies with age

1. Infancy - Y-shape
2. Juvenile - T-shape
3. Adolescence - Jigsaw puzzle

As sutural patency is vital to R.M.E, it is important to know when does the suture closes by synostosis. On an average 5% of suture is closed by age 25 yrs. Earliest closure occurs in girls aged 15 yrs.

Slow Maxillary Expansion (SME)

Slow palatal expansion is a method employed to correct a narrow upper arch by gradually widening it transversely. This technique, also known as dentoalveolar expansion, utilizes appliances to broaden the palate. Although the expansion primarily affects the dental structure, noticeable skeletal changes also occur. The tissues surrounding the maxilla experience reduced resistance, and bone formation increases at the mid-palatine suture⁷.

Research has demonstrated that slow expansion ensures excellent post-expansion stability. A force of 10-20 newtons, generating 450-900 grams of force, is applied to the upper arch, which is insufficient to separate a maturing suture. With slow maxillary expansion, the upper arch width increases by 3.8 to 8.7mm, applying 900 grams of force at a rate of 1mm per week. Appliances used for slow maxillary expansion are categorized into removable and fixed types. Examples of removable devices include the Active Plate, Schwartz Appliances, and Coffin Springs, while fixed appliances include the Niti Palatal Expander, Quad Helix, and Spring Jet.

The quad helix expander, originally introduced by Ricketts, is designed to deliver expansion at a slower rate with a comparatively less rigid construction.

Its mechanism of action involves gradual palatal expansion by moving the maxillary molars buccally, rotating them distally, and activating the anterior arms to expand the premolar and canine regions. This approach is considered more physiologic than rapid maxillary expansion and may be associated with reduced relapse.

Boysen et al found that the quad helix can also produce a greater anterior expansion, resulting in an improved arch form, by taking the advantage of the anterior arms that delivers a "sweeping action"⁸.

Rapid Maxillary Expansion (RME)

According to the Cohen hypothesis, termination of growth is unrelated to closure of the sutures. Even if 95% of the growth of the maxilla ends at 7 years of age, the suture may not already be closed⁹. The various technologies that can be used to analyze the maxillary expansion include occlusal radiographs, multi-slice low dose CT, micro-CT, ultrasound, CBCT, hand and wrist method, cervical vertebrae method and fractal analysis. In some adults, the distribution of maturation stages revealed that the midpalatal suture may remain in a non-fused state. This suggested that the chronological age should not be the only factor used to determine whether SARPE or conventional RME can be performed in adult individuals.

An RME treatment performed in adults whose midpalatal suture is already ossified could induce a bending of the circum-maxillary structure, compression of the periodontal ligament, resorption of the buccal root in the posterior teeth, perforation of

the buccal alveolar bone, severe pain, periodontal side effects and gingival recession in the maxillary molar area.

As the separation of the maxillae progressed, it can be hypothesized that they were moved in an outward and possibly upward direction. The midpalatal edges of the maxillary palate moved in an outward direction as well. This combination of events not only resulted in a widening of the nasal cavity, but also a flattening of the roof of the oral cavity. On a lateral headplate this might extend an impression of a dropping or lowering of the nasal floor as illustrated by Haas. In actuality, it may possibly be a tilting of the nasal floor as the maxillae are moved in a lateral direction. This combination of reactions to the orthopedic procedure could conceivably result in a flattening of the palatal vault.

It has been expressed by Haas that patients clinically subjected to this procedure feel pressure in the vault of the palate, in the region of the alveolar processes, and in the frontonasal region. Some patients indicate a sensation of some pressure in the region of the cheeks and a spot slightly posterior to this area. Interestingly enough, this clinical reaction could be somewhat corroborated by the histologic reactions of the various remote sutures studied.

The sutures in the nasal area showed the greatest reaction to the maxillary expansion procedure. As the maxillae are separated at the level of the palate, the more superior aspects of these bones are changing in relation to adjacent bones. This explains the pressure that has been noted, clinically, at the bridge of the nose. The sutures in the area of the nasal complex were obviously disrupted. The second most active suture was found to be the zygomatic-maxillary suture and some adjustment was noted in as remote an area as the zygomatico-temporal suture¹⁰.

It could be hypothesized that the zygomatic bone was being moved as well as the maxillary bone. One could assume that the maxillary bones could move or slide along the maxillary-zygomatic suture permitting the development of a greater width to the maxillary palate. However, the fact that adjustment was noted in the zygomaticotemporal suture, even though it was minimal in nature, would tend to indicate that the zygomatic bone is being moved as well.

Understanding individual variability in the fusion of the mid palatal suture is essential in identifying prospectively which late adolescent or young adult patient can have RME as a less invasive alternative to surgically assisted expansion. The midpalatal suture has been described as an end to end type of suture with characteristic changes in its morphology during growth.

In the infantile period, Melsen reported that the midpalatal suture is broad and Y-shaped in its frontal sections. The ossification process in the midpalatal suture starts with bone spicules from suture margins along with "islands" (ie, masses of acellular tissue and inconsistently calcified tissue) in the middle of the sutural gap. The formation of spicules occurs in many places along the suture, with the number of spicules increasing with maturation and forming many scalloped areas that are close to each other and separated in some areas by connective tissue.

Concomitantly, interdigitation increases; then fusion occurs earlier in the posterior area of the suture, with progression of ossification taking place from posterior to anterior, with resorption of cortical bone in the sutural ends and formation of cancellous bone.

The start and the advance of fusion of the midpalatal suture vary greatly with age and sex. Persson and Thilander observed fusion of the midpalatal suture in subjects ranging from 15 to 19 years old. On the other hand, patients at ages 27, 32, 54, and even 71 years have been reported to have no signs of fusion of this suture. Such findings indicate that variability in the developmental stages of fusion of the midpalatal suture is not related directly to chronologic age, particularly in young adults. Thereby it is justifiable enough to say that skeletally, more of anterior expansion occurs and in terms of dentoalveolar we see greater transverse expansion in the posterior precisely the molar region, keeping into account the two individual variable entities i.e skeletal and dentoalveolar changes¹¹.

SARPE has the similar advantages with the conventional RME. However, notable disadvantages of SARPE include potential for pressure related non-infectious frank necrosis (occurred in approximately 1.8% of cases), bleeding and infection during surgery, joint pain, periodontal problems, recurrence and the need for surgery and hospitalization. In adult individuals whose midpalatal suture is already closed, SARPE should be performed instead of RME. Therefore, the maturation phase of the midpalatal suture must be accurately determined¹².

Elements of Growth

Growth at the mandibular condyles produces a forward component of the chin, not a downward, nor a downward and forward component. It is only when the vertical increments of facial growth begin to assert their influence on condylar growth through occlusal contact that a downward and forward direction of the chin is produced.

Thus, it can be said that condylar growth is pitted against the combined vertical elements of the growth. The final vector of growth of the chin is a resultant of the struggle between horizontal growth and vertical growth, in other words, between condylar growth and vertical growth of the molars.

These vertical "elements" of growth are specific areas where the increments tends to occur which produces an increase in facial height. They are as follows: (1) growth at nasion and in the corpus of the maxilla which produces an increase in the distance from nasion to anterior nasal spine and causes the maxillary molars and posterior nasal spine to move away from the sella-nasion plane, (2) growth of the maxillary posterior alveolar processes causing the molar teeth to move away from the palatal plane, and (3) growth at the mandibular posterior alveolar processes causing the molar teeth to move occlusally¹³.

The dorsal migration of the gleaned fossa is a significant factor in many cases and tends to cancel out the growth of the condyles; thus, in a sense it is arrayed on the side of vertical growth.

Clockwise rotation of the mandible is a result of more posterior vertical growth than condylar growth, the point of rotation being the condyles. When vertical growth exceeds horizontal growth, (condylar growth) pogonion cannot keep pace with the forward growth of the upper face and the mandibular plane must become steeper.

The question stands, what effect does this type of growth have upon treatment? Discernibly enough this condition would not help reduce the ANB angle, and it would not aid in correction of a Class II molar relation. However, it would tend to help correct the vertical overbite of the incisors.

Many such growth patterns actually do reduce the vertical overbite, perhaps the majority do not. There is ample evidence to

show that a predominance of vertical growth of the face facilitates the correction and retention of vertical overbite.

Counter clockwise rotation of the mandible is a result of more condylar growth than combined vertical growth. This type of rotation is nearly always accompanied by a forward movement of pogonion and an increase in the facial angle.

Hence, variation in growth at the condyles and at the molar area is responsible for the rotation of the corpus of the mandible.

In a study conducted by Pradeepraj et al, patients with a predominantly vertical growth pattern showed advanced skeletal age and dental age when compared with chronological age. Hence skeletal parameters such as Anterior facial height and posterior facial height would be more pronounced in case of vertical growers in comparison to their chronological age¹⁴. The pattern was the same for both male and female subjects. Delayed skeletal age and dental age as compared with chronological age were seen in horizontal growers. The pattern was the same for both male and female subjects. When the skeletal age was compared with the dental age of the subjects in each group, the vertical groups showed advanced dental age in both male and female subjects; the horizontal groups showed more advanced skeletal age in both male and female subjects. Thereby it was concluded that orthodontic therapy should be started earlier in patients with a predominantly vertical growth than those with a predominantly horizontal growth pattern.

Nasion Point Dynamics

Nasion is one of the three points which establish the angular relation of the maxilla to the mandible when ANB, which most clinicians employ to record this information, is used. Therefore, if this is an important link in the diagnostic chain of cephalometric analysis and if nasion does change regularly and to a significant extent, the introduction of this third variable could make ANB a poor reflection of apical base relationship. Freeman indicated this in his thesis and emphasized the importance of considering "the anteroposterior relation of the maxilla (point A) to the cranium (represented by point N).

Moore believed that variation, not constancy, was the rule. One significant observation was that two points, nasion and the pterygomaxillary fissure, previously thought to be relatively stable in all individuals, were proved to be highly variable during growth of some individuals¹⁵.

In a study with particular emphasis on positions of point A in the changing facial configuration, Baber and Meredith found that, with reference to nasion, the location of point A lies more inferiorly with increasing age¹⁶.

Moreover, Enlow described facial growth and included a detailed description of the frontal region. He noted that the forehead grows in a generally anterior and slightly superior direction which is accomplished by a process of resorption and deposition at the surfaces of the laminae, combined with an expanding diploe, producing a distinct drift of the forehead in an anterior direction.

Mini-screw Assisted Rapid Palatal Expansion (MARPE)

The MARPE appliance, introduced by Dr. Won Moon and colleagues, is an innovative adaptation of the traditional RME appliance and represents a major advancement in the correction of transverse malocclusions. It has established itself as a reliable and effective nonsurgical alternative for young adults.

Micro-implant Assisted Rapid Palatal Expansion (MARPE) appliances have been developed to direct expansion forces specifically to the midpalatal suture while minimizing stress on the

dentoalveolar structures. Among these, the Maxillary Skeletal Expander (MSE), first introduced around 2003, has undergone significant refinement over time. The MSE is uniquely designed to deliver expansion forces more posteriorly against the zygomatic buttress and pterygopalatine sutures, as well as more superiorly to the mid palatal and other superiorly positioned peri-maxillary sutures.

Unlike other mini-screw assisted RPE designs, the jackscrew in the MSE is positioned between the maxillary first molars, medial to the zygomatic buttress. For optimal stability, bicortical engagement anchoring into both the palatal and nasal cortical bone layers is recommended. This approach minimizes the risk of implant tipping within the bone and helps reduce internal strain¹⁷.

With MSE, the lateral force vectors generated during expansion are directed closer to the zygomatic buttress. Since the rotational fulcrum is positioned farther away, the expansion achieved is more translational in nature. As a result, unwanted effects such as lateral rotation of the maxillary halves, clockwise mandibular rotation, and subsequent bite opening can be significantly reduced.

Appliance Position

- **Anteriorly:** Distal to the third rugae along the anterior palate increases the primary stability due to thick palatal bone, propagating the forces to the naso-maxillary complex.
- **Middle:** On the flat palatal but thinner bone surface of second premolar region. This promotes a close contact area with the jackscrew but significantly increases the risk for bicortical penetration.
- **Posteriorly:** Immediately anterior to the soft palate, at the region of the first permanent molar. This results in an increased orthopaedic effect due to the resistance offered by the pterygoid plates.

Surgically Assisted Rapid Palatal Expansion (SARPE)

Brown (1938) was the first to propose SARPE as a treatment approach for TMD. The technique is founded on the principles of distraction osteogenesis later described by Ilizarov (1987). In SARPE, distraction forces are transmitted and applied to the bone using either tooth-borne or bone borne devices. It has proven to be a reliable method for managing TMD, producing stable and clinically effective long-term dental and skeletal changes¹⁸.

These skeletal changes are also manifested in the facial soft tissues. The most frequently reported effects include increased lateral projection of the cheeks and widening of the nasal base. Variations in treatment arise from differences in surgical techniques, the type of appliance used to achieve expansion, and the specific expansion protocol followed. Recent systematic reviews, however, have reached varying conclusions regarding the necessity of pterygoid plate separation. In addition, the impact of SARPE on nasal airway volume has also been the subject of recent investigations.

Indications of SARPE¹⁹

1. To increase the maxillary arch perimeter, correct posterior crossbite and when no additional surgical jaw movements are planned.
2. To widen the maxillary arch as a preliminary step, even when further orthognathic surgery is anticipated helping to reduce risks, inaccuracies, and instability linked with segmental maxillary osteotomy.
3. To create space for a crowded maxillary dentition in cases where extractions are not indicated.

4. To correct maxillary hypoplasia associated with cleft palate.
5. To reduce wide black buccal corridors when smiling.

Conclusion

Interceptive treatment when paired with appropriate rehabilitation, can help restore normal growth and jaw function. Generally, the older the patient, the more pronounced the dental effects and the less significant the skeletal changes. RME, often performed with tooth/tissue-borne appliances (such as Hyrax or Haas), produces immediate results by applying heavy forces over a short duration.

In contrast, SME typically involves appliances like a coil spring or quad helix, which use continuous, low forces over a longer period, and are considered to offer a more physiological approach with better sutural stability.

Expansion of the maxilla and maxillary dentition can be achieved through various approaches. The choice of method is largely determined by the underlying skeletal and dental pattern and selecting the appropriate type of expansion can significantly enhance the effectiveness of the overall treatment plan.

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